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Analysis of Occupational Accident Narratives in the Manufacturing Sector Using Latent Dirichlet Allocation

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ABSTRACT

Despite advances and technological innovations in the field of occupational safety, workplace accidents remain a major economic and social problem. New risks emerge as work processes become more complex, and this affects employee health, productivity, and economic sustainability. As a result, the study's goal is to investigate sectoral errors that contribute to occupational accidents in the manufacturing sector. In this context, approximately 1,800,000 occupational accident descriptions obtained from the Social Security Institution (SGK) were analyzed using natural language processing and text mining techniques to identify patterns in accidents, determine thematic structures, and thus gain a better understanding of the underlying root causes. In this context, pre-processing steps (text cleaning, root finding, lemmatization), and Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) method were applied, and hidden structures were revealed with unsupervised learning algorithms. The findings enable the evaluation of occupational accidents in narrative-based dimensions and provide new perspectives for decision-makers in developing preventive strategies for errors made on a sectoral basis.

1 INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing sector is critical to the development of many countries, not only because of its employment dimensions, but also because of the economic and developmental benefits it provides. However, due to its high labor requirements and risky nature, it is one of the industries with the highest workplace accident rates. Workplace accidents not only endanger employees' health and lives, but they also cause significant economic and social problems. As a result, ensuring its long-term viability and providing safe working conditions are critical.

Many studies on occupational accidents in the manufacturing sector have been conducted using various methods, both nationally and internationally, and efforts have been made to prevent occupational accidents. Carillo-Castrillo et al. (2013) examined official accident investigation reports to identify the most common causes of accidents in the manufacturing sector in Andalusia, Spain, and to prioritize preventive measures taken by law enforcement. The study discovered differences in

causality between severe and fatal accidents, and the underlying mechanisms were investigated [1]. Chong et al. (2018) conducted a survey of 300 organizations to investigate the relationship between internal control and success factors influencing safety performance in Malaysia's manufacturing sector, and found that internal control practices are critical for high safety performance [2]. Liu et al. (2023) proposed an information entropy and LDA-based model for analyzing construction safety accidents. The study examined accident reports in the construction industry to determine the root causes of accidents, concluding that they were "failure to detect safety hazards in a timely manner" and "inadequate management of construction site safety" [3].

As a result, the study sought to examine the most common occupational accidents and errors that occur during economic activities in the manufacturing sector. The Social Security Institution of the Republic of Türkiye provided the occupational accident descriptions section of approximately 1,800,000 occupational accident notification reports for analysis. Using the topic modeling method Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), the study identified topics and errors from data divided into 24 sectors. It was determined that occupational accidents had not previously been analyzed on a sectoral basis using the LDA method, so it fills a gap in the literature. The research critical for analyzing occupational accidents in the manufacturing sector, taking preventative measures, and creating safe working environments.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Manufacturing Sector

The manufacturing sector encompasses a wide range of activities, including the production of goods from raw materials, assembly line operations, metal product manufacturing, and the setup, use, repair, and operation of heavy machinery and equipment. The economic activities included in the manufacturing sector, according to the sectoral classification of the Ministry of Labor and Social Security, are shown in Table 1. Analyzing workplace accidents in the manufacturing sector, which employs a sizable proportion of the workforce, is critical due to the high risk of these work environments. Workplace accidents not only endanger employee safety and physical and mental health, but they also incur significant economic costs. Several factors contribute to workplace accidents in the manufacturing industry [4], [5]. These include insufficient safety protocols, insufficient management, human errors, operational errors, machinery malfunctions, and hazardous working conditions. To prevent workplace accidents, administrative and regulatory measures, employee training, collective protection measures, the establishment of a safety culture, ergonomic designs, and facility layouts must all be implemented.

Table 1 Classification of Economic Activities in the Manufacturing Sector

Sector Code	Economic Activities
10	Manufacture of Food Products
11	Manufacture of Beverages
12	Manufacture of Tobacco Products
13	Manufacture of Textiles
14	Manufacture of Wearing Apparel
15	Manufacture of Leather and Related Products
16	Manufacture of Wood, Wood and Cork Products, and Woven Goods Made from Straw, Reed and Similar Materials
17	Manufacture of Paper and Paper Products
18	Printing and Reproduction of Recorded Media
19	Manufacture of Coke and Refined Petroleum Products
20	Manufacture of Chemicals and Chemical Products
21	Manufacture of Basic Pharmaceutical Products and Pharmaceutical Preparations
22	Manufacture of Rubber and Plastic Products
23	Manufacture of Other Non-Metallic Mineral Products

24	Manufacture of Main Metals
25	Manufacture of Fabricated Metal Products (Except Machinery and Equipment)
26	Manufacture of Computer, Electronic and Optical Products
27	Manufacture of Electrical Equipment
28	Manufacture of Machinery and Equipment N.E.C. (Not Elsewhere Classified)
29	Manufacture of Motor Vehicles, Trailers and Semi-Trailers
30	Manufacture of Other Transport Equipment
31	Manufacture of Furniture
32	Other Manufacturing
33	Setup and Repair of Machinery and Equipment

2.2 Data

The data used in this study was obtained from the Social Security Institution (SGK) as workplace accident reports in the manufacturing sector covering the period 2012-2023. Accident reports were entered in Turkish by the person reporting the accident to the SGK, explaining the cause and how the accident occurred. The number of accident reports by sector is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Number of Accident Report by Sector

Sector Code	Data	Sector Code	Data	Sector Code	Data
10	169909	18	7800	26	13833
11	4937	19	1498	27	81637
12	1169	20	33440	28	96901
13	167915	21	7823	29	109864
14	49539	22	107779	30	55250
15	7885	23	118452	31	56319
16	30979	24	141901	32	10905
17	30447	25	209512	33	42979

2.3 Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA)

Topic modeling is a text mining method based on unsupervised learning that discovers hidden themes in data. It was proposed in the 1980s, based on the topic field of "generative probabilistic modeling," where observed data interact with unobservable and hidden parameters in a certain probabilistic relationship [6]. Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) was proposed as a topic modeling method by Blei, Ng, and Jordan in 2013. LDA is a generative probabilistic model of a corpus and structures the data at three levels: word, topic, and document [6], [7].

LDA assumes a generative process for each document (w) in the corpus (D), the steps of which are shown below [7].

1. Choose N number of words. $N \sim Poisson(\xi)$
2. Select the topic distribution for the document named θ . $\theta \sim Dir(\alpha)$
3. For every N word w_n :
 - a. Choose a topic. $z_n \sim Multinomial(\theta)$
 - b. Choose a word from the word distribution of the topic. $w_n \sim p(w_n|z_n, \beta)$

In summary, the basic idea of LDA is based on modeling each document as a mixture of topics and assigning each word to topics according to its probability of appearing in a topic [8]. LDA can be used in many different areas such as social network analysis, scientific literature summary, knowledge discovery and summarization, user comment analysis, and news classification [9].

2.4 Method of the Study

The study conducted a work-related accident error analysis based on accident descriptions from 24 economic activities within the manufacturing sector. The sectors included in the study were determined based on the Turkish Social Security Institution (SGK) classification: manufacture of

food products, manufacture of beverages, manufacture of tobacco products, manufacture of textiles, manufacture of wearing apparel, manufacture of leather and related products, manufacture of wood, wood and cork products, and woven goods made from straw, reed and similar materials, manufacture of paper and paper products, printing and reproduction of recorded media, manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products, manufacture of chemicals and chemical products, manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations, manufacture of rubber and plastic products, manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products, manufacture of main metals, manufacture of fabricated metal products (except machinery and equipment), manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products, manufacture of electrical equipment, manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c. (not elsewhere classified), manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers, manufacture of other transport equipment, manufacture of furniture, other manufacturing, setup and repair of machinery and equipment.

The LDA method, a topic modeling method, was chosen for error analysis. The data used in the study was first preprocessed. This preprocessing process involved converting to lowercase letters and removing punctuation and numbers. Since the data was in Turkish, stop-word cleaning and lemmatization were performed using the nltk library. A bigram model was created to identify phrases with high semantic coherence. To determine the optimal number of topics in the LDA method, num_topic values between 2 and 10 were tested, and coherence scores were calculated. The number of topics with the highest coherence score was determined as the ideal number of topics for the data, which was segmented by sector. After determining the optimal number of topics, the LDA model was trained with the Gensim Library, and the parameters were kept constant. The model's output was evaluated using the perplexity metric and coherence scores (CV, UMass, UCI, and NPMI), which measure the model's predictive success.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The LDA method was used in the study to analyze the occupational accident descriptions of 24 manufacturing sectors, resulting in the identification of the most common occupational accidents on a sector basis.

3.1 Manufacture of Food Products

In the food manufacturing sector, 169909 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 6, with a score of 0.4378, as shown in Figure 1. Figure 2 depicts the semantic distance between topics. Topics 1, 2, 3, and 5 are close together, while topics 4 and 6 are distinct from the rest. Topic 4 has a marginal distribution when compared to other topics, but it accounts for 2% of total documents. This indicates that topic 4 is a rare theme. Topic 1 is the most prevalent theme in the dataset.

Figure 1 Manufacture of Food Products Optimal Topic Number

Figure 2 Manufacture of Food Products Intertopic Distance Map

The analysis revealed that the key words for Topic 1, such as "cleaning," "eye," and "arm," refer to occupational accidents like eye contact and arm injuries caused by water or chemical splashes while cleaning. The key words for Topic 2 are "pallet," "fall," and "ground," which represent foot injuries caused by slips and falls. This indicates that falls or slips occur due to floors or pallets, and the most commonly affected limb is the foot. While topics 3 and 4 do not report a workplace accident error, they do represent clusters of statements reporting accidents involving employees who were transported to the hospital following the accident. These statements may be vague, end with "result: hospital transfer," and are written in formal report language. For Topic 5, key words such as hand, finger, machine, between, and band refer to occupational accidents involving hand/finger entrapment in machinery and conveyor systems. This could indicate an incident on the transportation, production, or filling conveyors. For Topic 6, key words such as hand, finger, knife, and cut refer to occupational accidents caused by direct contact with knives or cutting tools. Table 3 shows the analysis of accidents errors in the food manufacturing sector.

Table 3 Accident Error Analysis for Manufacture of Food Products

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	cleaning, eye, result, staff, do, during, wash, arm, boiler, water	Cleaning-related eye/arm injury
2	foot, result, fall, staff, pallet, ground, onto, fall, right, safe	Slip/fall-related foot injury
3	staff, hospital, then, work, be, go, be, hospital_referral, hospital send, done	Hospital referral injuries (general)
4	employee, work_accident, department, date_time, pass, named, vicinity, table, sack, historical	-
5	hand, finger, machine, right, result, left, between, band, work, staff	Machine-induced hand and finger compression
6	hand, finger, left, knife, cut, right, staff, result, work, during	Knife-related hand/finger injuries

The analysis yielded the following results: CV score of 0.4378, UMass of -2.9182, UCI of 0.1171, NPMI of 0.0310, and Perplexity (log) metric of -7.5315. Although these scores appear to indicate an average level of model success, they are sufficient for explaining work-related accidents in texts with short sentences and a lack of semantic integrity.

3.2 Manufacture of Beverages

In the beverage manufacturing sector, 4937 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 7, with a score of 0.3931. Topics 1, 2, 3, 4, and 6 are closely related, but Topics 2, 5, and 7 differ from the others, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Manufacture of Beverage Intertopic Distance Map

For Topic 1, key words such as vehicle, crash, and service refer to workplace accidents involving service vehicles in or near the factory. In Topic 2, prominent words like pallet, glass, bottle, and demijohn indicate pallet overturns, falls while carrying glass or demijohns, and eye injuries. For Topic 3, prominent words such as machine, hand, cover, and demijohn indicate hand/finger injuries while working with machinery, as well as workplace accidents caused by placing or removing demijohn lids. For Topic 4, prominent words such as bottle, eye, and chemical indicate chemical spills or eye contact while transporting bottles or crates. For Topic 5, common words such as foot, slide, ground, and pallet refer to workplace accidents such as carrying materials on pallets on slippery surfaces or slipping around machinery. For Topic 6, key words such as hand, finger, machine, and line refer to workplace accidents involving hand/finger entrapment on bottling lines, filling machines, or conveyor belts. For Topic 7, key words such as palette, chemical, and boiler refer to workplace accidents involving chemical exposure and subsequent hospitalization. Table 4 depicts the accident error analysis in the beverage industry.

Table 4 Accident Error Analysis for Beverage Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	personnel, vehicle, result, agent, accident, crash, service, factory, foot, service vehicle	Service vehicle crash / transport accidents
2	pallet, staff, glass, bottle, result, demijohn, place, employee, eye, empty	Injury during bottle and glass handling
3	work_accident, employee, machine, date_time, hand, left, challenge, cover, demijohn, done	Hand/finger injuries
4	result, during, challenge, case, right, bottle, eye, chemical, foot, left	Chemical exposure / eye-face contact

5	foot, result, staff, fall, left, slide, ground, machine, right, pallet	Slipping and falling-related foot and body injuries
6	hand, finger, machine, result, right, bottle, left, staff, line, work	Machinery or lines-related hand/finger injuries
7	hospital, staff, incident, pallet, chemical, inside, boiler, employee, be	Chemical exposure

As a result of the analysis, the CV score was calculated as 0.3931, UMass as -2.9147, UCI as -0.8393, NPMI as -0.0134, and Perplexity (log) metric as -7.5777.

3.3 Manufacture of Tobacco Products

In the tobacco products manufacturing sector, 1169 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 10, with a score of 0.2922. Figure 4 shows that all clusters, with the exception of topics 8 and 9, are well separated.

Figure 4 Manufacture of Tobacco Product Intertopic Distance Map

For Topic 1, key words such as place, machine, fall, and hit refer to accidents involving falls and collisions on stairs, boxes, and areas. For Topic 2, prominent words such as hand, car, parcel, and box refer to occupational accidents such as cuts or bruises from carrying parcels. For Topic 3, prominent words like foot, fall, and table refer to occupational accidents such as hand and foot injuries caused by slips and falls, as well as accidents involving contact with objects such as tables and parcels. While words like ladder, pipe, and line are prominent in Topic 4, they indicate a general report for workplace accident reporting. Words like lid, box, cigarette, and eye are prominent in Topic 5, indicating eye or arm injuries during material changes on the cigarette production line. Words like hand, finger, machine, and service_vehicle are prominent in Topic 6, indicating hand finger injuries while working at the machine, particularly those resulting from contact with service vehicles or machinery. Words like finger, knife, hand, machine, and cut are prominent in Topic 7, indicating workplace accidents resulting from cuts or compression of fingers resulting from direct contact with cutting tools or machinery. For Topic 8, the prominence of words such as machine, hand, and finger indicates occupational accidents caused by contact with machinery. The prominence of words like head, cage, and impact in Topic 9 indicates occupational accidents caused by head trauma from hitting something like a ceiling or obstacle. This topic also focused heavily on official occupational accident reporting. For Topic 10, the prominence of words such as foot, pallet, conveyor, impact, and type indicate occupational accidents caused by foot injuries from pallet overturning or falls on the conveyor system.

Table 5 Accident Error Analysis for Tobacco Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	place, personnel, area, worker, foot, ladder, machine, box, fall, hit	Falling/collision accidents in stairs, boxes, and areas
2	hand, vehicle, outcome, right, box, left, finger, foot, personnel, package	Hand or foot collision/cutting accidents while carrying box
3	foot, personnel, outcome, right, place, left, fall, finger, box, table	Foot and hand injuries resulting from falls
4	outcome, work, do, left, queue, ladder, pipe, take, line, place	-
5	personnel, outcome, right, left, foot, lid, arm, box, cigarette, eye	Accident occurred in the lid, box, cigarette line
6	hand, right, worker, finger, outcome, due_to, machine, front, service vehicle, side	Hand-finger amputation, machine contact
7	finger, hand, machine, left, knife, outcome, right, cut, box, between	Cutting with a knife, jamming between machines
8	machine, hand, outcome, work, place, finger, fall, right, worker, personnel	Hand-finger machine accidents
9	outcome, incident_occurred, found, hand, left, collision, right, foot, cage, head	Head and hand trauma, general reporting of the incident
10	foot, pallet, hit, left, fall, conveyor, work, located, tobacco, right	Pallet/foot strike – tobacco tape accident

As a result of the analysis, the CV score was calculated as 0.2922, UMass as -4.2687, UCI as -1.9776, NPMI as -0.0472, and Perplexity (log) metric as -7.2092.

3.4 Manufacture of Textiles

In the textiles manufacturing sector, 167915 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 10, with a coherence score of 0.4015. Figure 5 shows that clusters 1 and 5 are similar, as are clusters 2, 3, 4, and 6, while clusters 7, 9, and 10 are well separated.

Figure 5 Manufacture of Textile Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1's key words, hand, finger, machine, between, right, left, fabric, compress, and cylinder, refer to occupational accidents such as hand fingers becoming trapped in machinery. Topic 2's key words, wick, machine, while working, momentary, hand, finger, left, and needle, refer to occupational accidents caused by carelessness when handling wicks or needles. Topic 3 discusses workplace accident reporting and referral to a general hospital. Topic 4's key words, work_accident, result, eye, pass, date_time, paint, and chemical, refer to occupational accidents such as eye damage caused by chemical exposure in a chemical dyehouse. Topic 5's key words include car, foot, fabric, coil, right, left, hit, and pain, all of which refer to workplace accidents that resulted in fabric and coil impacts,

as well as foot injuries. The most prominent words in Topic 6 are hand, cut, finger, left, hook, coil, thread, and right, all of which refer to hand injuries caused by hooks and cutting tools. Topic 7's key words include head, hit, door, iron, head, cafeteria, kneecap, and metal, referring to workplace accidents involving head impacts and metalwork. Topic 8's key words, including result, injury, carelessness, measure_gel, collision, accident, work, and light, refer to workplace accidents that resulted in minor injuries due to carelessness. Topic 9's key words, including foot, fall, result, upon, ground, fall, right, left, pallet, and slip, refer to occupational accidents caused by slips or falls, which typically result in foot injuries. Topic 10's key words, including machine, clean, do, arm, cover, right, part, and row, refer to workplace-specific unspecified cover-related accidents as well as occupational cleaning accidents. Table 6 shows the accident error analysis for the textile sector.

Table 6 Accident Error Analysis for Textile Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	hand, finger, between, machine, right, left, fabric, squeeze, work, roller	Machines-related hand/finger trapping
2	roving, machine, while_working, sudden_moment, hand, finger, left, outcome, worked, needle	Wick-needle accidents / carelessness
3	personnel, worker, hospital_transfer, after, hospital, treated, work, service, hospital_sent, go	Hospital referral injuries (general)
4	work_accident, outcome, eye, experience, personnel, worker, date time, date, dye, chemical	Chemical-dyehouse accidents
5	vehicle, foot, fabric, right, pain, bobbin, left, hit, outcome, taken to hospital	Fabric and bobbin impact-related foot injury
6	hand, left, cut, finger, hook, bobbin, outcome, yarn, right, clean	Hooks and cutting tools-related hand injuries
7	head, hit, door, iron, occurred, sprain, skull, cafeteria, metal, kneecap	Head impact/metal field injuries
8	outcome, injury, inattention, occurred, collision, personnel, work, casualty, while, minor	Minor injuries – carelessness
9	foot, fall, outcome, onto, place, right, falling, left, pallet, slip	Slips and falls-related foot injuries
10	machine, do, cleaning, arm, cover, hit, right, existing, section, while	Cleaning / lid-related arm injuries

As a result of the analysis, the CV score was calculated as 0.4010, UMass as -3.4205, UCI as -0.1764, NPMI as 0.0155, and Perplexity (log) metric as -7.9532.

3.5 Manufacture of Wearing Apparel

In the wearing apparel manufacturing sector, 49539 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 9, with a coherence score of 0.4723. Figure 6 shows that clusters 3 and 5 are similar, as are clusters 1, 2, and 4, while clusters 6, 7, 8, and 9 are well separated.

Figure 6 Manufacture of Wearing Apparel Intertopic Distance Map

For Topic 1, prominent words such as hand, finger, fabric, left, cut, scissors, outcome, cutting, right, and work refer to workplace accidents involving hand injuries caused by sharp objects. Topics 2 and 4 are generally about workplace accidents that require hospitalization. For Topic 3, key words such as vehicle, between, product, hand, hit, work, right, door, left, and table refer to workplace accidents involving collisions in transportation/production areas. For Topic 5, key words like eye, personnel, iron, machine, outcome, do, hit, while working, during, and piece refer to workplace accidents involving eye contact with machinery and ironing. Topic 6's use of words such as casualty, provided, water, chemical, take, during, protective, back, cabinet, and boiler indicates workplace accidents caused by chemicals and a failure to use personal protective equipment. For topic 7, the prominence of words such as finger, machine, hand, outcome, left, work, needle, sewing, personnel, and right denotes accidents such as fingers getting caught in machines and sewing accidents. For topic 8, the prominence of words such as foot, outcome, fall, place, falling, right, personnel, work_accident, left, and onto indicates workplace accidents caused by falls, which usually result in foot injuries. For topic 9, the use of words such as service, outcome, vehicle, personnel, car, accident, front, service_vehicle, occurred, and collision indicates workplace accidents involving service vehicles.

Table 7 Accident Error Analysis for Wearing Apparel Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	hand, finger, fabric, left, cut, scissors, outcome, cutting, right, work	Cutting tools-related hand injuries
2	done, hospital_transfer, treated, first_aid, after, by, date_time, personnel, none, around	Hospital referral injuries (general)
3	vehicle, between, product, hand, hit, work, right, door, left, table	Collision incidents in the transportation/production area
4	worker, personnel, after, hour, work_accident, section, one, hospital, date, during	-
5	eye, personnel, iron, machine, outcome, do, hit, while_working, during, piece	Machine and ironing-related eye injury
6	casualty, provided, water, chemical, take, during, protective, back, cabinet, boiler	Chemicals/protective equipment shortage
7	finger, machine, hand, outcome, left, work, needle, sewing, personnel, right	Machine/sewing-related hand/finger injury
8	foot, outcome, fall, place, falling, right, personnel, work_accident, left, onto	Fall-related foot injuries
9	service, outcome, vehicle, personnel, car, accident, front, service_vehicle, occurred, collision	Service vehicle-related accidents

3.6 Manufacture of Leather and Related Products

In the leather and related products manufacturing sector, 7885 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 4, with a coherence score of 0.2997. Figure 7 shows that clusters 2 and 4 are well separated while clusters 1 and 3 are little similar.

Figure 7 Manufacture of Leather and Related Products Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1 features the words hand, finger, outcome, left, cut, knife, leather, do, right, and machine, all of which refer to workplace accidents caused by cutting tools. Topic 2 describes workplace accidents that resulted in hospitalization. For Topic 3, the key words hand, machine, finger, outcome, work, mold, right, left, personnel, and inattention refer to workplace accidents involving a hand caught in a machine or in the mold area. For Topic 4, the key words foot, outcome, fall, falling, place, onto, arm, work_accident, personnel, and left refer to workplace accidents that result in injuries, particularly to the feet and arms as a result of falls. Table 8 shows the Accident Error Analysis for Leather and Related Product Manufacturing.

Table 8 Accident Error Analysis for Leather and Related Products Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	hand, finger, outcome, left, cut, knife, leather, do, right, machine	Cutting tools-related hand/finger injury
2	personnel, after, hospital, work, worker, work_on, go, done, date, treated	Hospital referral injuries (general)
3	hand, machine, finger, outcome, work, mold, right, left, personnel, inattention	Machine and mold area-related hand injury
4	foot, outcome, fall, falling, place, onto, arm, work_accident, personnel, left	Fall-related foot and arm injuries

3.7 Manufacture of Wood, Wood and Cork Products, and Woven Goods Made from Straw, Reed and Similar Materials

In the wood, wood and cork products, and woven goods made from straw, reed and similar materials manufacturing sector, 30979 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 4, with a coherence score of 0.4248. Figure 8 shows that clusters 3 and 4 are well separated, whereas clusters 1 and 2 are slightly similar.

Figure 8 Manufacture of Wood Intertopic Distance Map

For topic 1, the key words foot, outcome, fall, falling, onto, right, left, place, occurred, and injury refer to workplace accidents that resulted in falls from heights and foot injuries. For topic 2, the prominent words hand, cover, hit, between, press, belt, personnel, line, board, and arm refer to workplace accidents caused by being struck by or trapped in machinery. For topic 3, the prominent words hand, finger, outcome, machine, left, right, piece, work, injury, and wood refer to workplace

accidents that resulted in machine-related finger and hand injuries. The most prominent words in topic 4 refer to workplace accident reporting processes. Table 8 displays the accident error analysis.

Table 9 Accident Error Analysis for Wood Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	foot, outcome, fall, falling, onto, right, left, place, occurred, injury	Falls/height-related foot injuries
2	hand, cover, hit, between, press, belt, personnel, line, board, arm	Machine part-related collision/squeeze
3	hand, finger, outcome, machine, left, right, piece, work, injury, wood	Machinery-related finger and hand injuries
4	personnel, eye, worker, after, during, work, machine, hospital, work on, date	-

3.8 Manufacture of Paper and Paper Products

In the paper and paper products manufacturing sector, 30447 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 9, with a coherence score of 0.4111. Figure 9 shows that clusters 1 and 2 are highly similar, clusters 3 and 5 are slightly similar, while clusters 4, 6, 7, 8, and 9 are distinct.

Figure 9 Manufacture of Paper and Paper Products Intertopic Distance Map

Topics 1 and 6 discuss general workplace accident reports. For topic 2, prominent words such as machine, hand, between, finger, right, jam, work, trapped, left, and personnel refer to workplace accidents such as a hand becoming caught in machinery and finger injuries. For topic 3, prominent words like eye, come, boiler, dye, splash, neck, side, placed, present, and caustic refer to workplace accidents caused by chemical exposure to facial areas like the eyes and neck. For topic 4, key words like foot, fall, outcome, personnel, onto, right, left, place, ladder, and slip refer to workplace accidents caused by falls from ladders or heights. For topic 5, the key words pallet, outcome, foot, personnel, work_accident, product, occurred, left, right, and collision refer to workplace accidents that occur during pallet and load handling. For topic 7, the key words reel, paper, experience, work_accident, shaft, machine, during, vehicle, outcome, and right refer to workplace accidents caused by pieces falling from coils, mish, and rotating parts. For topic 8, the words hit, outcome, cover, head, do, cleaning, pipe, region, located, and during all refer to workplace accidents that resulted in head and body injuries as a result of collisions while cleaning. For topic 9, the key words hand, finger, outcome, left, right, machine, cut, knife, occurred, and injury refer to workplace accidents involving hand amputations and machine knife accidents.

Table 10 Accident Error Analysis for Paper and Paper Products Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	personnel, worker, hospital_transfer, after, hospital, treated, date time, being, date, work	-
2	machine, hand, between, finger, right, jam, work, trapped, left, personnel	Machinery-related finger/hand injuries/trapped
3	eye, come, boiler, dye, splash, neck, side, placed, present, caustic	Chemical substance / eye contact incidents
4	foot, fall, outcome, personnel, onto, right, left, place, ladder, slip	Stairs and heights-related falling
5	pallet, outcome, foot, personnel, work_accident, product, occurred, left, right, collision	Pallet and cargo handling-related accidents
6	hospital_referred, truck, hoop, unexpected, rail, dismantling, however, escape, drum, by stepping	-
7	reel, paper, experience, work_accident, shaft, machine, during, vehicle, outcome, right	Coil, shaft and rotating part accidents
8	hit, outcome, cover, head, do, cleaning, pipe, region, located, during	Cleaning, pipe-related head/body injuries
9	hand, finger, outcome, left, right, machine, cut, knife, occurred, injury	Machine/knife-related hand/finger injury

3.9 Printing and Reproduction of Recorded Media

In the printing and reproduction of recorded media manufacturing sector, 7800 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 8, with a coherence score of 0.3917. Figure 10 shows that clusters 2 and 3 are highly similar, clusters 5 and 7 are slightly similar, while clusters 1,2,6, and 8 are separated.

Figure 10 Manufacture of Printing and Reproduction of Recorded Media Intertopic Distance Map

Topics 1, 2, and 7 represent general workplace accident reports. For topic 3, the frequent use of words like hospital_transfer, personnel, treated, hospital, after, work, worker, infirmary, one, and onto indicates workplace accidents that necessitate hospital transfer. For topic 4, the frequent use of words like machine, section, worker, cutting, hand, press, left, as_operator, and currently_working indicates workplace accidents involving cutting and printing machines that resulted in hand injuries. For topic 5, the use of words such as hand, finger, machine, left, right, outcome, cut, knife, work, and between indicates workplace accidents caused by cutting tools, which typically result in finger injuries or amputations. For topic 6, the prominence of words such as eye, outcome, machine, personnel, hit, do, one, accident, impact, and present indicates workplace accidents involving crash and eye injuries. Topic 8's use of words such as foot, fall, pallet, outcome, reel, left, onto, ground, right, and falling indicates workplace accidents caused by pallet falls that result in foot injuries.

Table 11 Accident Error Analysis for Printing Products Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	work_accident, pain, worker, personnel, experience, work, occurred, hospital, section, arm	-
2	head, paint, tea, order, person, pressure, worker, pain, laborer, around_time	-
3	hospital_transfer, personnel, treated, hospital, after, work, worker, infirmary, one, onto	Hospital referral injuries (general)
4	machine, section, worker, cutting, hand, press, left, as_operator, currently_working	Risks caused by cutting/printing machines
5	hand, finger, machine, left, right, outcome, cut, knife, work, between	Hand/finger amputation with a cutting tool
6	eye, outcome, machine, personnel, hit, do, one, accident, impact, present	Eye injuries and crash-related accidents
7	outcome, hand, inattention, personnel, machine, work, injury, occurred, right, impact	General work accidents / carelessness
8	foot, fall, pallet, outcome, reel, left, onto, ground, right, falling	Pallet-related falls/foot injuries

3.10 Manufacture of Coke and Refined Petroleum Products

In the coke and refined petroleum products media manufacturing sector, 1498 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 2, with a coherence score of 0.2997. Figure 11 shows that clusters 1 and 2 are highly separated.

Figure 11 Manufacture of Coke and Refined Petroleum Intertopic Distance Map

For topic 1, the use of words like hand, right, finger, left, outcome, valve, field, foot, worker, and after indicates workplace accidents caused by valves and field work, which typically result in hand and finger injuries. For topic 2, the prominence of words such as outcome, foot, hand, left, right, fall, worker, personnel, finger, and pain indicates workplace accidents that resulted in hand and foot injuries caused by falls.

Table 12 Accident Error Analysis for Coke and Refined Petroleum Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	hand, right, finger, left, outcome, valve, field, foot, worker, after	Hand-finger injuries in the valve and field
2	outcome, foot, hand, left, right, fall, worker, personnel, finger, pain	Falls related hand-foot injuries

3.11 Manufacture of Chemicals and Chemical Products

In the chemicals and chemical products manufacturing sector, 33440 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 4, with a coherence score of 0.4269. Figure 12 shows that clusters 1 and 2 slightly similar while clusters 3 and 4 are highly separated.

Figure 12 Manufacture of Coke and Refined Petroleum Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1 covers general workplace accident reports. Topic 2 covers workplace accidents that resulted in foot injuries due to falls caused by foot, outcome, fall, personnel, pallet, ground, right, left, onto, impact, and floor. Topic 3 makes extensive use of words like hand, finger, machine, outcome, left, right, between, work, cut, and jam, indicating workplace accidents that result in hand and finger injuries caused by machinery. Topic 4 makes extensive use of words like eye, outcome, personnel, during, production, chemical, product, line, hose, and do, indicating workplace accidents caused by chemical exposure in chemical production processes.

Table 13 Accident Error Analysis for Coke and Refined Petroleum Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	personnel, worker, after, work, hospital, hospital_transfer, date_time, treated, box, hospital_sent	-
2	foot, outcome, fall, personnel, pallet, ground, right, left, onto, impact	Pallets and floors-related foot injuries
3	hand, finger, machine, outcome, left, right, between, work, cut, jam	Machine-related hand and finger injuries
4	eye, outcome, personnel, during, production, chemical, product, line, hose, do	Eye and exposure injuries during the chemical manufacturing process

3.12 Manufacture of Basic Pharmaceutical Products and Pharmaceutical Preparations

In the basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations manufacturing sector, 7823 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 10, with a coherence score of 0.3884. Figure 13 shows that although the clusters appear close, they are separated, and topic 1 covers the most general topic.

Figure 13 Manufacture of Pharmaceutical Products Intertopic Distance Map

The key words in Topic 1 are personnel, pallet, outcome, foot, impact, worker, work_accident, occurred, date_time, and material, all of which refer to workplace accidents caused by pallets that typically result in foot injuries. The key words in Topic 2 are foot, fall, outcome, ground, ladder, personnel, onto, slip, falling, and worker, all of which refer to accidents on stairs and floors. Topic 3's key words, cart, autoclave_cart, tray, personnel, pull, product, between, waste, hand, and left, refer to accidents involving autoclave and tray transportation. Topic 4 discusses major accidents involving machinery and collisions. Topic 7 covers occupational accidents caused by chemical splash, while Topic 8 deals with occupational accidents caused by chemical exposure in laboratories. Topics 9 and 10 cover occupational accidents caused by machinery-related injuries to the hands, fingers, or feet.

Table 14 Accident Error Analysis for Pharmaceutical Products Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	personnel, pallet, outcome, foot, impact, worker, work_accident, occurred, date_time, material	Pallet-related foot injuries
2	foot, fall, outcome, ground, ladder, personnel, onto, slip, falling, worker	Fall accidents caused by stairs and floors
3	cart, autoclave_cart, tray, personnel, pull, product, between, waste, hand, left	Autoclave and tray transportation-related accident
4	work_accident, outcome, experienced, one, collision, hand, date_time, right, machine, left	Machinery and collision-related general work accidents
5	foot, personnel, area, after, work, outcome, right, arm, worker, left	-
6	personnel, outcome, vehicle, car, accident, back, impact, service, incoming, left	Service vehicle-related traffic accidents and collisions
7	eye, personnel, after, chemical, hose, boiler, splash, product, process, come	Chemical splash-related eye injuries
8	outcome, during, laboratory, solution, hand, bottle, splash, quality_control, face, during	Liquid splash and face contact in laboratory environment
9	hand, finger, machine, personnel, right, left, outcome, work, cut, trapped	Hand and finger injuries from working with machinery
10	machine, between, hand, disc, metallic, numbered, motor, right, foot, cotton	Mechanical equipment-related hand/foot trapping

3.13 Manufacture of Rubber and Plastic Products

In the rubber and plastic products manufacturing sector, 107779 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 3, with a coherence score of 0.4123. Figure 14 demonstrates that all clusters are well separated.

Figure 14 Manufacture of Rubber and Plastic Products Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1 addresses foot injuries caused by floors and pallets. Topic 2 discusses hand injuries caused by dies and coils, while Topic 3 discusses machinery-related hand and finger injuries. Topic 4 addresses general workplace accident reports that result in hospital transfers.

Table 15 Accident Error Analysis for Rubber and Plastic Products Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	oot, outcome, fall, personnel, ground, falling, pallet, onto, right, left	Floors and pallets-related foot injuries
2	hand, mold, between, reel, right, machine, left, finger, jam, impact	Die and coil-related hand stuck
3	hand, finger, outcome, machine, left, cut, right, work, personnel, occurred	Machine-related hand and finger injuries
4	personnel, worker, eye, after, work, machine, hospital, hospital transfer, work on, treated	-

3.14 Manufacture of Other Non-Metallic Mineral Products

In the non-metallic mineral products manufacturing sector, 118452 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 10, with a coherence score of 0.4267. Figure 15 demonstrates that all clusters are well separated except clusters 1, 3 and 5.

Figure 15 Manufacture of Non-Metallic Mineral Products Intertopic Distance Map

Topics 4 and 9 cover general workplace accidents, whereas Topic 1 focuses on machinery-related hand and finger injuries. Topic 2 addresses stone and marble falls, while Topic 3 deals with vehicle and concrete equipment accidents. Topic 5 addresses workplace accidents caused by falls from heights, Topic 6 addresses hand and arm amputations caused by glass cutting, and Topic 7 addresses accidents caused by contact with mold and metal parts. Topic 8 addresses pallet-related foot and leg injuries, while Topic 10 addresses accidents caused by carelessness in the packaging and tape areas.

Table 16 Accident Error Analysis for Non-Metallic Mineral Products Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	hand, finger, left, between, right, outcome, machine, sign, head, work	Machine-related hand and finger injuries
2	outcome, stone, foot, marble, machine, slab, falling, piece, hand, right	Stone and marble-related fall
3	eye, outcome, vehicle, personnel, do, car, pump, concrete, mixer, work accident	Vehicles and concrete equipment-related accident
4	personnel, accident, worker, date_time, during, date, occurred, after, outcome, hospital transferred	-
5	foot, outcome, fall, ground, falling, left, right, onto, personnel, slip	Foot injuries due to falls from heights or slips
6	glass, hand, outcome, right, left, personnel, arm, during, cut, cutting	Hand and arm injuries during glass cutting
7	mold, head, hit, cover, iron, impact, metallic, during, skull, work	Hit accidents with molds and metal parts
8	pallet, crate, product, hospital_sent, wood, onto, leg, dropped, existing, empty	Leg and foot injuries due to pallet falls
9	treated, pain, car, hospital_transfer, hospital, work, section, furnace, first_aid, done	-
10	belt, outcome, right, tile, inattention, packaging, hand, left, none, receive	Accidents caused by carelessness in the packaging and tape area

3.15 Manufacture of Main Metals

In the main metals manufacturing sector, 141901 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 8, with a coherence score of 0.3924. Figure 16 demonstrates that all clusters are similar except clusters 7 and 8.

Figure 16 Manufacture of Main Metals Products Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1 discusses workplace accidents resulting in falls and foot injuries caused by materials. The second topic discusses hand injuries that occur while handling parts and cutting sheet metal. Topic 3 discusses workplace accidents that result in eye injuries and how they relate to general accident reporting. Topic 4 discusses accidents involving eye burns caused by casting and hot

materials. Topic 5 discusses accidents involving heavy lifting and pain, while Topic 6 discusses risks encountered in packaging and wire coil processes. Topic 7 discusses crane and pipe collision-related head and body injuries, while Topic 8 discusses workplace accidents involving material and machine interaction.

Table 17 Accident Error Analysis for Main Metals Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	foot, outcome, fall, right, left, onto, falling, material, work, iron	Falls and foot injuries – material-related risks
2	piece, hand, left, burr, right, sheet_metal, cut, belt, take, do	Hand injuries during part handling and sheet metal cutting
3	personnel, outcome, worker, work_accident, work, section, do, eye_burr, during, date_time	Eye related injuries
4	outcome, during, work, eye, hot, right, furnace, casting, injury, left	Eye-burn injuries caused by castings and hot materials
5	pain, cover, formation, waist, crate, person, swelling, sand, work, use	Heavy lifting related pain
6	hospital_transfer, treated, casualty, package, wire, reel, being, hoop, done, infirmary	Risks in the packaging and wire-coil process
7	personnel, pipe, hit, crane, outcome, collision, material, head, basket, worker	Crane and pipe collision-related head and body injuries
8	hand, finger, left, between, outcome, right, material, jammed, work, during	Hand and finger jamming – material and machine interaction

3.16 Manufacture of Fabricated Metal Products (Except Machinery and Equipment)

In the fabricated metal products manufacturing sector, 209512 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 8, with a coherence score of 0.4075. Figure 17 demonstrates that all clusters are well separated, except clusters 1 and 4.

Figure 17 Manufacture of Fabricated Metal Products Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1 covers occupational accidents caused by eye injuries in welding and processing. Topic 2 covers occupational accidents that resulted in foot injuries from heights or ground-based work. Topic 3 covers hand and finger trapping accidents caused by mold and machinery. Topic 4 covers occupational accidents caused by amputated hands and fingers during sheet metal cutting. Topic 5, while not specifying a specific cause, suggests that eye and hand injuries are common. Topic 6, despite being a generalized accident report, shows that hospital admissions have occurred. Topic 7 covers occupational accidents involving falls and collisions caused by materials and pallets. Topic 8 is about occupational accidents that cause head injuries due to impact.

Table 18 Accident Error Analysis for Fabricated Metal Products Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	eye, welding, machine, do, burr, personnel, piece, wire, process, worker	Eye injuries during welding and processing
2	foot, fall, outcome, onto, falling, ground, right, left, work, slip	Foot injuries caused by heights or the ground
3	hand, finger, between, left, right, piece, outcome, mold, machine, material	Hand-finger trapping between mold and machine
4	hand, finger, sheet_metal, left, cut, right, piece, laceration, outcome, take	Hand and finger cuts during sheet metal cutting
5	outcome, hand, work_accident, do, work, injury, personnel, piece, occurred, eye_burr	Accidents resulting in hand and eye injuries
6	personnel, hospital, pain, treated, worker, after, hospital_transfer, work, hour, date	Hospital referral injuries (general)
7	material, outcome, foot, personnel, right, pallet, left, crate, profile, during	Crash/fall accidents caused by materials and pallets
8	personnel, one, head, hit, worker, work, place, after, door, back	Head injury due to impact

3.17 Manufacture of Computer, Electronic and Optical Products

In the computer, electronic and optical products manufacturing sector, 13833 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 7, with a coherence score of 0.4646. Figure 18 demonstrates that all clusters are well separated, except clusters 1 and 6.

Figure 18 Manufacture of Computer, Electronic and Optical Products Intertopic Distance Map

The key words in Topic 1 are hand, finger, machine, personnel, left, right, work, outcome, piece, and cut, which refer to household and finger work-related accidents involving machinery use. Topic 2's key words, personnel, fall, foot, worker, ground, in_water, hit, onto, eye, and work, refer to accidents involving falls and foot injuries caused by ground contact. Topic 3's key words, foot, personnel, outcome, left, right, vehicle, basket, during, section, and shift, refer to occupational accidents caused by foot impacts sustained during vehicle and equipment movements. Topic 4 describes occupational accidents involving shuttle vehicles. Topic 5 describes occupational accidents caused by impacts sustained by workers working on conveyor and belt lines. Topic 6 describes occupational accidents caused by negligence. Topic 7 covers general occupational accident reports that require hospitalization.

Table 19 Accident Error Analysis for Computer, Electronic and Optical Products Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	hand, finger, machine, personnel, left, right, work, outcome, piece, cut	Machine use-related hand and finger injuries
2	personnel, fall, foot, worker, ground, in_water, hit, onto, eye, work	Floor-related falls and foot injuries
3	foot, personnel, outcome, left, right, vehicle, basket, during, section, shift	Vehicle and equipment movement-related foot impact
4	work_accident, experienced, outcome, impact, traffic_accident, service_vehicle, J_plate, vehicle, shift_entry, external_physical	Service vehicle-related traffic and collision accidents
5	outcome, right, during, hand, work_accident_occurred, conveyor, left, material, pallet	Conveyor and belt line related hand impact
6	outcome, inattention, material, worker, injury, foot, negligence, hand, fall, superficial	Carelessness and imprudence related injuries
7	personnel, head, worker, after, done, one, treated, work, hospital_transfer, hospital	Hospital referral injuries (general)

3.18 Manufacture of Electrical Equipment

In the electrical equipment manufacturing sector, 81637 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 7, with a coherence score of 0.4467. Figure 19 demonstrates that all clusters are well separated, except clusters 2 and 4, 6 and 7.

Figure 19 Manufacture of Electrical Equipment Products Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1 covers occupational accidents involving material-related hand impacts. Topic 2 covers workplace accidents involving machinery-related hand and finger compressions. Topic 3 is about workplace accidents that require hospitalization. Topic 4 addresses occupational accidents caused by falling materials. Topic 5 covers occupational accidents that result in hand or finger amputations caused by sheet metal and mold welding. Topic 6 covers painful occupational accidents caused by assembly and conveyor lines. Topic 7 covers occupational accidents involving box-lid impact injuries during panel assembly.

Table 20 Accident Error Analysis for Electrical Equipment Products Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	work_accident, outcome, experienced, hand, left, right, impact, during, material, belt	Material-related hand impact
2	hand, finger, machine, between, left, right, worker, outcome, work, do	Machinery related hand/finger entrapment

3	personnel, worker, after, eye, hospital_transfer, treated, work, section, date, during	Hospital referral injuries (general)
4	foot, outcome, personnel, material, fall, ground, falling, right, onto, pallet	Material fall-related injury
5	hand, finger, outcome, left, sheet_metal, right, work, cut, material, mold	Sheet metal and mold welding-related hand/finger cut
6	work_accident_occurred, accident_experienced, belt, during, outcome, right, left, pain, assembly, cabinet	Assembly and conveyor line-induced pain
7	impact, panel, assembly, machine, shift_entry, arm, occurred, box, line, cover	Box-lid impact related injuries during panel assembly

3.19 Manufacture of Machinery and Equipment N.E.C. (Not Elsewhere Classified)

In the machinery and equipment manufacturing sector, 96901 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 4, with a coherence score of 0.3893. Figure 20 demonstrates that all clusters are well separated, except clusters 1, and 2.

Figure 20 Manufacture of Machinery and Equipment Products Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1 covers occupational accidents caused by machinery and sheet metal-related hand-finger jams. Topic 2 discusses accidents that necessitate a referral to a general hospital. Topic 3 covers material-related foot injuries. Topic 4 covers occupational accidents caused by eye contact with flying burrs while welding or grinding.

Table 21 Accident Error Analysis for Machinery and Equipment Products Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	hand, finger, outcome, left, piece, right, material, between, machine, sheet metal	Machinery and sheet metal material related hand-finger jams
2	personnel, worker, after, hospital, date_time, during, work, work on, treated, hospital transfer	Hospital referral injuries (general)
3	foot, outcome, material, fall, falling, personnel, onto, right, ground, left	Material fall related foot injury
4	outcome, do, eye, welding, personnel, grinding, burr, eye_burr, pipe, process	Burrs flying during welding and grinding related eye injuries

3.20 Manufacture of Motor Vehicles, Trailers and Semi-Trailers

In the machinery and equipment manufacturing sector, 109864 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 8, with a coherence score of 0.4185. Figure 21 demonstrates that all clusters are well separated, except clusters 1, and 3.

Figure 21 Manufacture of Motor Vehicles, Trailers and Semi-Trailers Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1 covers workplace accidents involving rims and impact-related operator injuries. Topic 2 is about general workplace accidents that require hospitalization. The third topic discusses pallet and floor-related falls and foot injuries. Topic 4 discusses workplace accidents that resulted in hand and finger injuries from molds and machinery. Topic 5 discusses workplace accidents involving welding and sanding. Topic 6 discusses workplace accidents that resulted in hand and finger injuries during part cutting. Topic 7 covers workplace accidents involving eye injuries from welding and grinding. Topic 8 addresses general workplace accident reporting statements.

Table 22 Accident Error Analysis for Motor Vehicles, Trailers and Semi-Trailers Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	operator, impact, rim, worker, cover, existing, line, shift, head, after	Rim and impact-related operator injuries
2	date_time, personnel, pain, work, hospital_transfer, treated, hospital, worker, after, during	Hospital referral injuries (general)
3	foot, fall, right, left, onto, outcome, pallet, ground, impact, worker	Pallet and floor related falls and foot injuries
4	hand, finger, left, mold, right, between, piece, machine, outcome, jammed	Mold and machine related hand-finger jams
5	casualty, welding, incoming, outcome, occurred, workshop, material, sanding, metal, happened	Welding and sanding related accidents
6	piece, hand, left, finger, outcome, crate, right, cut, sheet_metal, take	Part cutting related hand and finger injuries
7	eye, welding, do, eye_burr, grinding, burr, splash, right, personnel, left	Welding and grinding related eye injuries
8	outcome, material, work_accident, occurred, personnel, injury, work, hand, impact, during	-

3.21 Manufacture of Other Transport Equipment

In the machinery and equipment manufacturing sector, 55250 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 5, with a coherence score of 0.4321. Figure 22 demonstrates that all clusters are well separated, except clusters 1, and 2.

Figure 22 Manufacture of Other Transport Equipment Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1's key words, ship, do, nb_ship, hit, pipe, machine, head, assembly, unit, and work, refer to head impact accidents involving ship assembly and piping operations. Topic 2 describes occupational accidents that necessitate hospitalization. Topic 3 refers to occupational accidents involving foot injuries caused by falls on stairs or floors. Topic 4 describes occupational accidents involving hand and finger trapping due to material and pipe. Topic 5 describes occupational accidents caused by burr spatter during welding and grinding.

Table 23 Accident Error Analysis for Other Transport Equipment Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	ship, do, nb_ship, hit, pipe, machine, head, assembly, unit, work	Ship assembly and piping operations related head impact
2	infirmery, treated, hospital_transfer, personnel, pain, go, hospital, after, date, work	Hospital referral injuries (general)
3	foot, fall, outcome, personnel, right, left, work, ladder, onto, falling	Stairs and floors related falls and foot injuries
4	hand, finger, outcome, left, right, piece, material, between, personnel, pipe	Material and pipe related hand and finger trapping
5	personnel, eye, work, do, eye_burr, outcome, welding, grinding, splash, done	Welding and grinding related burr spatter - eye accidents

3.22 Manufacture of Furniture

In the machinery and equipment manufacturing sector, 56319 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 5, with a coherence score of 0.5022. Figure 23 demonstrates that clusters 1, 2, and 4 are mostly similar, except clusters 3, and 5.

Figure 23 Manufacture of Furniture Intertopic Distance Map

Topics 1 and 5 are about general occupational accidents that require hospitalization. Topic 2 discusses occupational accidents resulting in hand and finger amputations caused by machinery. Topic 3 discusses the consequences of hand and head injuries caused by production processes. Topic 4 covers occupational accidents caused by ground irregularities and material-related falls, which result in foot injuries.

Table 24 Accident Error Analysis for Furniture Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	personnel, work, after, eye, one, hospital, date_time, work, employee, date	-
2	hand, finger, outcome, machine, piece, left, right, cut, work, injury	Machine-induced hand-finger amputations
3	hand, left, finger, outcome, during, do, work, head, department, sofa	Production process related hand and head injuries
4	foot, outcome, material, right, fall, falling, personnel, onto, left, during	Ground irregularities and material-related falls and food injury
5	outcome, occupational_accident, control, employee, limb_loss, injury, undergo, severe, treated, hospital transfer	Hospital referral injuries (general)

3.23 Other Manufacturing

In the other manufacturing sector, 10905 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 5, with a coherence score of 0.4964. Figure 24 demonstrates that clusters 3, 4, and 5 are well separated, except clusters 1, and 2.

Figure 24 Manufacture of Furniture Intertopic Distance Map

Topic 1's key words, such as foot, outcome, personnel, fall, employee, onto, falling, hand, place, and right, refer to occupational accidents involving foot injuries caused by falls from heights and materials. Topic 2 describes workplace accidents involving food poisoning and service accidents. Topic 3 addresses machine-related hand-finger cuts and mold accidents. Topic 4 deals with hand injuries caused by assembly and production processes. Topic 5 also includes service and occupational accidents requiring hospitalization.

Table 25 Accident Error Analysis for Furniture Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	foot, outcome, personnel, fall, employee, onto, falling, hand, place, right	Heights or material-related falling / foot injury
2	personnel, occupational_accident, one, due_to, company, section, food_poisoning, lunch, determined, outsourced_service	Workplace food poisoning and service-related accidents
3	hand, outcome, finger, left, piece, machine, right, personnel, cut, mold	Machine-related hand-finger cuts and mold accidents
4	machine, hand, finger, work, right, left, personnel, outcome, assembly, employee	Assembly and production-related hand injuries
5	outcome, service, after, hospital, personnel, door, go, hit, impact, work	Service accidents and hospital process

3.24 Setup and Repair of Machinery and Equipment

In the setup and repair of machinery and equipment sector, 42979 data descriptions were analyzed, and the number of topics was found to be 6, with a coherence score of 0.4490. Figure 25 shows that clusters 1, 2, and 3, as well as clusters 4 and 6, are similar, while cluster 5 stands out from the others.

Figure 25 Manufacture of Setup and Repair of Machinery and Equipment Intertopic Distance Map

The most prominent words in Topic 1 are work, eye, perform, result, welding, personnel, eye_spark, left, part, and hand, all of which refer to welding and assembly-related eye injuries. Topic 2's key words include occupational_accident, experience, vehicle, person, car, result, employee, front, personnel, and trunk, all of which refer to vehicle-related work accidents and injuries during transportation. Topic 3 refer to assembly and piping-related hand and finger injuries. Topic 4 refer to falling from heights or falling onto materials-related foot injuries. The key words in Topic 5 are personnel, located, place, cable, order, hit, area, one, pipe, and being, all of which refer to work-related accidents. Workplace accidents requiring hospitalization are among the most common words in Topic 6.

Table 26 Accident Error Analysis for Setup and Repair of Machinery and Equipment Manufacturing

Topic No	Topic Keywords	Topic
1	work, eye, perform, result, welding, personnel, eye_spark, left, part, hand	welding and assembly work-related eye injury
2	occupational_accident, experience, vehicle, person, car, result, employee, front, personnel, trunk	vehicle-related work accidents and injuries during transportation
3	hand, finger, result, left, right, between, pipe, material, part, during	assembly and piping related hand and finger injuries
4	foot, result, fall, right, work, falling, left, personnel, material, place	falling from heights or falling onto materials related foot injuries
5	personnel, located, place, cable, order, hit, area, one, pipe, being	wiring and pipe related accident
6	personnel, hospital, after, sent, go, infirmary, hospital_transfer, employee, work, shift	hospital referral injuries (general)

As a result of the research, 24 sectors were analyzed using the LDA method, and an error analysis was performed based on the most frequent sector-specific accidents. The study serves as a guide for improving working conditions, fostering a safety culture, and ensuring the long-term viability of work environments in a large sector like manufacturing, which occupies significant social and economic space.

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